

NetDRIVE Workshops

Oxford University

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Introduction.....	4
Workshop Questions.....	4
Agenda	4
Consolidated Outcomes and Actions	5
Notes	8
Breakout group feedback.....	8
Breakout Group 1 Notes and Conclusions.....	8
Breakout Group 2 Conclusions:	9
Breakout Group 3 Notes and Conclusions.....	9
Question 1: How do negative emotions, values, and incentives enter into decision processes?.....	9
Question 2: What motivates you and the people around you?.....	10
Question 3: Can we enhance the role of positive emotions, values, and incentives?.....	10
Early career focus	11
Breakout Group 4 (& 3 for final session) Conclusions	11
Survey Feedback.....	12
Attendees.....	13

Meeting page: <https://eng.ox.ac.uk/netdrive/events/>

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Introduction

The workshop took place at Keble College's H B Allen Centre, 25 Banbury Road, Oxford OX2 6NN.

The meeting included delegates from a wide range of backgrounds and career stages. Keynote speakers provided informative and inspirational context, and delegates were then asked to examine three key questions in breakout groups.

The feedback from the groups is included at the end of this report, together with a consolidated summary.

Workshop Questions

With the aim of helping exploration of new perspectives, the formulation of the three questions for this meeting was drawn from Pope Francis [Laudato Si', 2015; 1] and Patriarch Bartholomew [2], who provide a theological perspective on climate change. Laudato Si' calls for a new form of collective action and reiterates Patriarch Bartholomew's comments on the need to turn away from "fear, greed and compulsion".

Question 1: How do negative emotions, values, and incentives enter into decision processes?

- How to fear, greed, and compulsion get reflected in the workspace?
- What are the barriers and triggers that initiate negative approaches?

Question 2: What motivates you and the people around you?

- What is the point University research?
- When work is great, what is making it great?
- Do you believe you can be effective in advancing sustainability personally or collectively with colleagues?

Question 3: Can we enhance the role of positive emotions, values, and incentives?

- Exploiting the positive motivational factors that people bring to work?
- Can we bring more self-awareness, generosity, and wonder into our work?
- Can we create a Working Group to develop a transformational ethical framework?

References: 1: <https://bit.ly/LaudatoSi> ; 2: <https://bit.ly/Ustein2003>

Agenda

8:30 Welcome and coffee	
9:00 – 10:30 Session 1	
	Welcome and Introduction to Meeting [10 minutes]

	NetDRIVE and Meeting Objectives
	Keynote 1: Oxford Net Zero [Sam Fankhauser]
	Briefing for breakouts
10:30	Coffee Break
10:45	Session 2
	Breakout 1: Collecting our thoughts
	Keynote 2: NC3Rs [Elliot Lilley]
12:15	Lunch
13:45	Session 3
	Breakout Feedback
14:00	Keynote 3: Zero Institute, Oxford [Paul Shearing]
	Breakout 2: Early career focus: enhancing opportunities and enabling research impact with sustainable resource usage
15:15	Afternoon Tea and Coffee
15:30	Session 4
	Feedback and review of meeting objectives
	Breakout 3: Tasks, Actions, Commitments
	Plenary Discussion
	Wrap-up
5:00	Meeting Closes
5:30	Drinks reception

Consolidated Outcomes and Actions

This consolidated list groups together issues raised by different groups into nine main discussion points. The relevant breakout group feedback is labelled in the format “X.Y”, where “X” is the breakout group number.

1. Mitigate risk of perceived or actual negative impact of net zero policy on science: empower people to achieve better research outputs. Draw on link between sustainability and greater clarity for career paths, particularly at the early career stage. [1.1,1.4]
 - a. Promote benefits of open science and requirements for protection of IPR.
 - b. Support development of institutional networks by providing guidance [4.3]
2. Training in sustainability, drawing on existing activities. [1.10]

- a. Engage with organisations to embed training for staff in practise. [1.2,1.5]
 - b. Develop guidelines on sustainability plans for projects
 - c. Clarity and support for sustainable career pathways (e.g. green software engineers, but also green machine room operations etc.) [2.6]
 - d. Sustained funding for skill development and software curation [2.7]
 - e. Tools to support decision making in context of competing drivers, such as desire to avoid idle equipment vs. avoiding unnecessary power draw. [3.2]
3. Identify silos and act to bridge or tunnel between them [1.3]
- a. Look to global organisations, drawing on NC3Rs experience with WHO.
 - b. Support sustainable approaches to building of open and inclusive communities, particularly for ECR. [1.5]
 - c. Support sustainable approaches to international collaboration, particularly with respect to building communities and networks for ECRs [1.4, 3.14, 3.16]
 - d. Enhance interaction between research councils. [1.13]
 - e. A community approach to creating [new] behaviour norms. [2.2]
 - f. Explicit support for community approach in funded community activity or activities [4.7]
4. Reward, encourage, and mandate positive actions. [1.10, 2.1, 3.4]
- a. Engage with Research Excellence Framework to embed net zero in research practise and evaluation. [1.6, 2.4]
 - i. ACTION [Core Team]: Approach REF and propose a focus meeting in late 2025 or early 2026 to explore potential for inclusion of net zero metrics in the 2034 REF, building on engagement and research culture elements.
 - b. Giving awards to motivate people (or facilitate workplace reward processes) [1.7]
 - c. Develop guidance for inclusion of net zero awards in promotion and recognition schemes.
 - d. Explore approaches to motivational barrier associated with delayed and uncertain benefits (e.g. reducing footprint by reducing CPU usage has uncertain effect on overall DRI emissions [in the worst case, for an academic, no one notices] and even more uncertain effect on the climate). Encourage personal and institutional support for long term thinking. [2.1, 3.7]
 - e. Encourage and reward learning from different disciplines. [3.12]
 - f. Disseminate spotlight case studies, e.g. through webinars [1.12]
 - g. Support sustainability planning for projects, moving towards a mandatory scheme. [2.3]
 - h. Recognise and reward contributions to collective action [3.10]

- i. Learn from NC3Rs success in shifting international policy [4.4]
5. Tackle underlying causes of behaviour that undermines collective goals. [3.3]
 - a. Encourage open discussion of fears, frustrations, experiences, and concerns that may cause people to evade controls put in place for the collective good (e.g. hoarding storage or CPU, delaying sharing of critical data, spending quickly to avoid losing funds, need to establish personal reputation in early career, skipping training, ...). [3.1, 3.5, 3.6, 3.13]
 - b. Enhance automated feedback from facilities about resource usage. E.g. files held on high latency storage with no read requests, large CPU usage with minimal outputs [editor note: this may need some thought around documentation of workflows]. [3.8]
 - c. Provide informative comparative metrics.
 - d. Explore potential for Open Science concepts to protect people when they share new ideas [2.5]
 - e. Challenge work patterns that rely on instant access to resources. Look at the benefits of reflection before resource use. Challenge premises of legacy workflows and structures [3.11]
 - f. Challenge perception that high resource use is positive in itself. [3.8]
6. Early Career Support [4.5, 4.11]
 - a. Ring fence some 2nd call funds for a portfolio of early career projects. Launch this through a sandpit event at which can also act as a focal point for discussion of concerns. [4.6]
 - b. Early career forum [1.8]
 - c. Respect and build on factors that motivate researchers. [3.9]
 - d. Mentor scheme [3.15]
7. Focus meeting on specific NetDRIVE/roadmap challenge. [1.8]
 - a. Ethics
8. Provide more transparent information about NetDRIVE project and team. [1.9]
 - a. Develop a membership scheme [1.11]
 - b. Explore ways of facilitating connection between people and networks [4.1, 4.2]
 - c. Sharing best practice [4.11]
9. Developing better tools to support our collective goals [1.10]
 - a. Support FAIR compute [3.4]
 - b. Tools, in a broad sense, to enable broader appreciation of collective benefits [3.9]
 - c. Engage with journals to develop policy on carbon cost of research. [4.10]
 - d. Develop and continue approach of taking project to communities, exploiting interdisciplinary speakers to promote discussion [3.18, 4.8]
 - e. Active workshop focussed on specific area [4.13]

Notes

- UKRI has awarded funds to [3 projects exploring new approaches to collaboration](#) and [a new sustainable research hub](#).
- Details of current [REF review](#) are [here](#), with a pilot version of the [People, Culture, and \[work\] Environment](#) element here.

Breakout group feedback

We had four breakout groups; each group met three times during the course of the meeting. The notes below record the feedback provided by the nominated rapporteur of each group. For the final session several people had left, and so groups 3 and 4 were merged.

Breakout Group 1 Notes and Conclusions

- 1) There is a risk that the drive to net zero is perceived as impacting on the science you can do. It is important to get the messaging correct: we can empower people to do smart science. Existing tools can be used for this. A summary of existing resources would be useful. {1}
- 2) It would be good to provide training in sustainability. Perhaps NetDRIVE could draw on SSI's experience in delivering training. NetDRIVE could act as a coordinator around what kind of training is provided. Small amounts of funding might help with training if you know the community well. {2}
- 3) NetDRIVE could act as a link between existing silos, maybe initially within STFC. {3}
- 4) It would be good to address the problem of short-term contracts for early career researchers being focussed solely on a specific contract. Maybe NetDRIVE could do outreach to managers to include sustainability in promotion criteria. {1,3}
- 5) When joining an organisation, everyone should have training in environmental sustainability to try and integrate it into the culture. Perhaps NetDRIVE should raise environmental issues with organisations. {2,3}
- 6) Perhaps there is an opportunity for NetDRIVE to be organised in the REF to recommend good practice. {4}
- 7) NetDRIVE could be involved in giving awards. {4}
- 8) NetDRIVE could provide an early career forum and also an ethics forum. {6}
- 9) It would be good to know the capabilities of the NetDRIVE team. {8}
- 10) Behaviour change might come from training, recognition, and the use of tools. {2,4,9}
- 11) Maybe NetDRIVE could provide a membership scheme similar to that being tried by HPC-SIG. {8}

- 12) NetDRIVE could provide spotlight case studies as a way of communicating success stories and building a repository of good news. This could be done through quarterly webinars. {4}
- 13) NetDRIVE could facilitate better interaction between research councils. {3}

Breakout Group 2 Conclusions:

- 1) Reward (e.g. money, career progression, status) research practice that we want to encourage. Develop clear guidance that makes best practice easy to implement, encouraging a shift from short- to long-term thinking. {4}
- 2) Champion a community approach for creating behaviour norms. Communities should be open and externally inclusive by design, including perspectives from outside the academic community. It should also be made clear that sustainability considerations need to be taken across all research disciplines. {3}
- 3) Sustainability plans for projects (analogous to data management plans) should be mandated by funders. {4}
- 4) Alternative metrics for determining project success should be developed, e.g. positive engagement with those benefitting from research. {4a}
- 5) A better structure for protecting people when they share new ideas should be developed and put in place, encouraging researchers to be more open. {5d}
- 6) Develop career pathways for sustainability e.g. Green RSEs. {2c}
- 7) Make long term funding available for researchers to support skills development and software maintenance. {2d}

Breakout Group 3 Notes and Conclusions

Question 1: How do negative emotions, values, and incentives enter into decision processes?

- How do fear, greed, and compulsion get reflected in the workspace?
 - What are the barriers and triggers that initiate negative approaches?
1. Greed - discussed anecdotal evidence, e.g. HPC users keeping access to compute by running programmes in background to avoid joining a queue for resource when they actually needed it. {5a}
 2. Challenge: want to use GPU at max all the time to make most of embodied emission {2e}
 3. Fear - unwillingness to share motivated by fear of losing out, not being able to deliver the research they need to do, pressures of deadlines. conferences etc. {5}
 4. Implementing FAIR principles to computing to promote sharing - FAIR use of compute {9}
 5. Funding example - will lose it if you don't spend it - fear of missing out [5a]

6. Then miss out on long-term considered choices because of pressure to spend budget quickly - need longer funding budget timeframes? → comes from experience of losing things in the past [5a]
7. Compulsion - 'on demand' nature of society, we expect instant access to computer resources like everything else [4d]
8. You do not get feedback from a computer like you used to when you are asking for a lot of compute as most of this is done externally e.g. on cloud [5b, 5f]
 - a. → There is a disconnect between what you are asking for and what it costs
 - b. people don't know that they ask for a lot, current view is that more data is better, e.g. high-resolution models [5f]
 - c. → On JASMIN there is no information about how much compute you are using compared to the average user - unclear comparatively how much you are asking for

Question 2: What motivates you and the people around you?

- What is the point University research?
 - When work is great, what is making it great?
 - Do you believe you can be effective in advancing sustainability personally or collectively with colleagues?
9. Motivations: [6c, 9b]
 - a. Feeling on top of things - a sense of succeeding
 - b. Having clear tasks/goals that you feel able to complete
 - c. Climate science background - tangible link between the science to how it affects society is motivating
 - d. Having an impact - making a change and seeing how it is useful
 - e. Applying what you know and using your skills to add value
 - f. Interest in the world and doing good for both the planet and society
 - g. Being able to see the end goal/outcomes of your actions is motivating, but often combatting climate change feels like reducing impact now for some unknown future - demotivating
 10. The power of collective action - knowing you are part of something big, e.g. Octopus energy study of paying customers for reducing their energy consumption for a day and then demonstrating the amount of energy saved in a tangible figure - demonstrates the impact of small things adding up to something big. {4h}
 11. We spoke about how the electricity grid is built on premise that they must keep up with demands at all times - actually could incentivise a decrease in demand. {5e}

Question 3: Can we enhance the role of positive emotions, values, and incentives?

- Exploiting the positive motivational factors that people bring to work?

- Can we bring more self-awareness, generosity, and wonder into our work?
 - Can we create a Working Group to develop a transformational ethical framework?
12. learning from different disciplines - can be inspiring, and promotes sharing of ideas {4e}

Early career focus

13. - data hoarding can be more tempting as an early career scientist as your first few outputs are important as you establish yourself in academia, ECRs have more at stake [5a]
14. - value of being present at international meetings when establishing yourself as an ECR conflicts with reducing carbon footprint from travel {3c}
15. - we talked about how one of the most valuable parts of conferences is getting together in person with international colleagues/connections - perhaps not the case for ECRs who don't have these connections? Value of the EGU Mentor scheme. {6d}
16. - we talked about our personal experiences of first attending large conferences as ECRs, many of us found smaller workshops easier for building connections, questioned the narrative that ECRs should be sent to large conferences to establish themselves - maybe there is value in finding a community first, when you don't know anyone {3}
17. - We talked about the value in finding a community as an ECR and how making meaningful connections has been easier at smaller events and workshops. As ECRs, focussing the type of conference that you can be most effective at {3}
18. - Net zero meetings - valued that the meetings are moving around instead of the people {9}

Breakout Group 4 (& 3 for final session) Conclusions

IDEAS:

1. More connections {8}
2. Network of networks {8}
3. Bootstrap how to (how to start a green network at your institute) {1}
4. Learn from NC3R's experience of developing World Health Organisation policy {4i}
5. Exchange of experience and ideas between ECR's and later career stage researchers {6}

Actions:

6. Ring fence funding for ECR lead community projects with proposal writing mentorship (perhaps via sandpit). {6}
7. Community collaboration demonstrator project: give community a task/action (maybe to schedule laptop battery usage to time shift grid energy usage) that can be monitored

and reported on. - ie feedback to motivate individual action and see the combined effect. {3f}

8. Continue to invite interdisciplinary speakers to NetDRIVE as they have sparked good ideas and conversations. [9c]
9. Learn from NC3Rs Development of policy by consensus - probably covered by NetDRIVE Network for Sustainable Change
10. Engage Journals to help draft policy - engage with FAIR principles - Carbon cost of research in an article. {9}
11. * Workshop for ECR {6}
12. - Share DRI use best practices {8}
13. - Active workshop to progress a specific NetDRIVE area. {9}

Survey Feedback

Attendees were asked to fill out a brief survey with three questions about their hopes and expectations for the transition to net zero DRI. On the belief that UKRI can achieve a meaningful net zero DRI by 2040, the delegates who responded were evenly divided (Figure 1). This contrasts with a strong positive feeling about the importance of achieving net zero (Figure 2). There was also a positive feeling about the ability of delegates to have a positive influence, with a means response of 3.5

Figure 1. Histogram of survey responses on belief in UKRI transition to net zero DRI.

Attendees

- Martin Juckes Oxford
- Sarah Sparrow Engineering Science
- Lucy Li University of Oxford
- Iago Perez Engeneering science
- Rafael Cesario de Abreu University of Oxford
- Graeme Smith University of Oxford
- David McDonagh STFC
- Kelly Widdicks UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
- Man-Suen Chan Department of Physics
- Sarah Hanrahan STFC
- Lorna Smith EPCC, The University of Edinburgh
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- Cuicheng Zhang Engineering Science
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- Sarah Callaghan University of Oxford
- Zhijin Guo University of Oxford
- Kirsty Pringle EPCC
- Elliot Lilley NC3Rs
- Jessica Huntley STFC